

Delivery guide: climate mosaic activity

A how-to-guide for anyone wishing to deliver a public engagement activity about inspiring conversations about climate change

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Who is this guide for?

This guide is intended for use by anyone wanting to organise a fun climate science craft activity.

You may want to use it to:

- Engage with people about environmental science, data and digital skills
- Interact and network with a group of people
- Create an artwork to inspire conversations about climate change

Summary of the activity

The warming stripes (image below) are a simple visual way to represent our planet's changing climate. Talking about our changing climate is one of the most powerful ways we can encourage positive change.

Graphics and lead scientist: Ed Hawkins, National Centre for Atmospheric Science, UoR. <https://showyourstripes.info/>

This activity combines environmental science, data and digital skills, art and creativity to inspire conversations about climate change.

The warming stripe colours are based on average yearly temperatures for your chosen location over a certain time period. Blue indicates cooler temperatures, red indicates warmer. The example we use in this guide uses data for Harwell, Oxfordshire (UK) over the last 3-4 generations (100+ years).

Anyone can freely access all the data, tools and knowledge you need to produce a personalised climate stripe for anywhere in the world. This guide describes how to do this, and provides examples of how to use the real environmental data to create an artwork.

In this guide we primarily show an example of using mosaic tiles - but other art mediums could be used.

Aim of the activity

The primary goal is to co-create a large mosaic artwork (3m x 0.5m) representing local temperature changes over the last 130 years, serving as a visual tool to inspire conversations about climate change.

The activity aims to empower visitors by showing how science and creativity intersect, encouraging them to discuss local climate impacts and feel hopeful about collective action.

How to create a custom warming stripe

Anyone can generate custom warming stripes for any location on Earth using the CEDA Web Processing Service (WPS) tool. The process involves selecting data (what, when, where), subsetting it to get average yearly temperatures, assigning colour codes based on average yearly temperature anomalies, and exporting the results to a table for use in crafts.

The instructions below walk you through the process of using the tool so you can generate your unique climate visualisation.

1. Navigate to <https://www.ceda.ac.uk/outreach/>

The screenshot shows the CEDA Outreach page. At the top left is the CEDA logo and name: "Centre for Environmental Data Analysis" with subtext "SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL" and "NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL". The top right navigation menu includes "News", "Events", "Status", "Projects", "Outreach", "TechBlog", "About", and a search icon. The main content area has a breadcrumb "Home / Outreach" and a large heading "Outreach". Below the heading is "5 MIN READ • 943 WORDS" and social sharing icons. A paragraph states: "Here we showcase the different resources we have available!". Another paragraph says: "At the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis we support lots of different environmental research. As part of this, it's important to share what we do and the impact that the science we support has on our planet." A third paragraph reads: "This page includes some activities that we have designed for public engagement events. If you wish to reuse this content, please credit this webpage." The "Warming Stripes" section features a horizontal bar chart with vertical stripes of varying colors (dark blue, light blue, white, red) representing temperature changes. Below the chart is the caption: "Warming stripes showing temperature change in Harwell, Oxfordshire". A text block explains: "The warming stripes are a simple visual way to represent our planet's changing climate - with each stripe representing the temperature of a single year." At the bottom, it says: "You can freely access all the data, tools and knowledge you need to produce your personalised climate stripe for a location within the UK - whether that's for your hometown, workplace or favourite holiday destination." A "Contact CEDA" button is in the bottom right corner.

2. Click "Use this tool to create your own personalised climate stripes!"

climate visualisation for your chosen location - whether that's your hometown, workplace or favourite holiday destination. We hope that this guide (available here as a PDF!) helps you to create your own warming stripes whilst encouraging conversations about climate change. Please send us photos of your creations!

Step 1: Choose a craft that you'd like to use

You could knit, crochet, paint, embroider, mosaic, bake or any other craft technique it is up to you.

Step 2: Gather craft materials

Try to recycle and reuse wherever possible! Plan how many colours you'd like to include in your stripe.

Step 3: Get the data for your chosen location

Use this tool to create your own personalised climate stripes!

It will create a PDF showing the data for a chosen UK location. You can choose the time period, how many colours to use and the latitude and longitude of your chosen location.

Create personalised climate stripes for anywhere in the world!

This tool functions the same but can be used for any country, not just the UK.

Step 4: Create!

Make your project using the climate data and your chosen craft.

Step 5: Share and talk about it

Show off your craft project with friends, family and even strangers! Can you display it in your window or share on your social media? We'd love to see pictures of your crafts too. Send pictures to support@ceda.ac.uk or tag us @cedanews on Twitter/X

Step 6: Inspire and take action

Talking about our changing climate is one of the most powerful ways we can encourage positive change. By sharing and talking, you can inspire others to take climate action. We hope we have inspired you to create your own warming stripes and encourage conversations about climate change.

On this page:

Warming Stripes
Try this activity at home
Example Craft Projects
Resources to support this activity

Contact CEDA

Example Craft Projects

- Choose either the UK ('plot climate stripes') or Global tool ('plot climate stripes global')

Compliance Checker Please choose one of the processes to submit a job.

A WPS for checking file compliance with standards such as CF

CF-Checker

Run the CF-Checker on a NetCDF file.

v1.0.0

Plot Climate Stripes

Plot your own climate stripes figure! Choose a start and end year and a location within the UK and we'll use this to make a personalised climate stripes image for your area. All we need is the latitude and longitude of your location, you can find this information at <https://www.latlong.net>. The programme will take a little while to run after submission. Once it has completed click 'Show Output' to view a pdf with your figure! The pdf has a table showing the breakdown of each year, the temperature for that year and the corresponding colour. It will also show you how many times each colour is used in the figure. You can find out more about climate stripes and discover inspiration for things to do with them here: <https://www.ceda.ac.uk/outreach>

v1.0.0

Plot Climate Stripes Global

Plot your own climate stripes figure! Choose a start and end year and a location and we'll use this to make a personalised climate stripes image for your area. All we need is the latitude and longitude of your location, you can find this information at <https://www.latlong.net>. The programme will take a little while to run after submission. Once it has completed click 'Show Output' to view a pdf with your figure! The pdf has a table showing the breakdown of each year, the temperature for that year and the corresponding colour. It will also show you how many times each colour is used in the figure. You can find out more about climate stripes and discover inspiration for things to do with them here: <https://www.ceda.ac.uk/outreach>

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- Add details to the form

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Processes Help - Sign In

Plot Climate Stripes Global

Please complete the form below and submit a job.

Plot your own climate stripes figure! Choose a start and end year and a location and we'll use this to make a personalised climate stripes image for your area. All we need is the latitude and longitude of your location, you can find this information at <https://www.latlong.net>. The programme will take a little while to run after submission. Once it has completed click 'Show Output' to view a pdf with your figure! The pdf has a table showing the breakdown of each year, the temperature for that year and the corresponding colour. It will also show you how many times each colour is used in the figure. You can find out more about climate stripes and discover inspiration for things to do with them here: <https://www.ceda.ac.uk/outreach>

[CEDA WPS UI](#) [CEDA WPS](#) [Disclaimer](#) <https://www.latlong.net> <https://www.ceda.ac.uk/outreach>

Project name

 Enter a name for your project

Latitude

 Latitude is how far the location is from the equator.

Longitude

 Longitude is how far the place is from the Prime Meridian. Anything East of this will be a positive number whilst anything West will be a negative number.

Number of Colours

 Enter the number of colours you'd like in your figure. The minimum is 5 and the maximum is 100, we recommend 20 colours.

Start year

 Enter the year you would like the data to start from. Note: most of the data starts in 1901.

End year

 Enter the year you would like the data to finish on. The last available year is 2023.

[Help ?](#)

- Click "Submit"
- Wait whilst the tool processes the data. Your screen will look something like below. If it hits an error, it will tell you. For example this one hits an error because the latitude/longitude is in the ocean - it needs to be on land.

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Processes Help - Sign In

Job Running [0/100]

```

1 0:00:02 0%: PyWPS Process PlotClimateStripesGlobal accepted
2 0:00:04 0%: PyWPS Process PlotClimateStripesGlobal accepted
3 0:00:06 10%: Begin data loading
4 0:00:08 10%: Begin data loading
5 0:00:10 10%: Begin data loading
6 0:00:15 10%: Begin data loading
7 0:00:20 10%: Begin data loading
8 0:00:25 10%: Begin data loading
9 0:00:30 10%: Begin data loading
10 0:00:35 10%: Begin data loading
11 0:00:45 10%: Begin data loading
12 0:00:55 10%: Begin data loading
13 0:01:05 10%: Begin data loading
14 ERROR: Process error: The chosen latitude and longitude returned no valid data. Please check that your selection included land points. - c
15 0:01:05 0%: Process error: The chosen latitude and longitude returned no valid data. Please check that your selection included land poin
  
```

- If the data processing works, it will show a green banner at the top. Click "Show Output" for a quick view of the detailed document. Or click 'details' for access to both the image file and detailed document.

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Processes Help - Sign In

Job Succeeded: [Show Output](#) [Details](#)

```

1 0:00:02 0%: PyWPS Process PlotClimateStripesGlobal accepted
2 0:00:04 0%: PyWPS Process PlotClimateStripesGlobal accepted
3 0:00:06 10%: Begin data loading
4 0:00:08 10%: Begin data loading
5 0:00:10 10%: Begin data loading
6 0:00:15 10%: Begin data loading
7 0:00:15 100%: PyWPS Process Plot Climate Stripes Global finished
  
```

8. You can now view and download your personalised climate stripes document and image file. The detailed document contains details of the data you requested, including a sample image of what the stripe looks like. The image file just shows the climate stripe, with no further information about the data.

Climate Stripes for:

London

Latitude: 51.5072°, Longitude: 0.1276°

Time period: (1901, 2023)

Using: 20 colours

Table 1: Temperature variations from the average, and colours per year.

years	temp_value	temp_demeaned	hex_colour	red	green	blue	colour	actual_colour
1901	9.21667	-0.66533	#74b2d4	0.45841	0.70031	0.83158	colour_06	
1902	8.81667	-1.06533	#3480b9	0.2066	0.50217	0.72673	colour_04	
1903	9.625	-0.257	#bddaac	0.74159	0.85841	0.91889	colour_08	
1904	9.6	-0.282	#bddaac	0.74159	0.85841	0.91889	colour_08	
1905	9.275	-0.607	#74b2d4	0.45841	0.70031	0.83158	colour_06	
1906	9.83333	-0.04867	#d9e8f1	0.85098	0.9129	0.94696	colour_09	
1907	9.40833	-0.47367	#9bcac0	0.61156	0.79236	0.88173	colour_07	
1908	9.175	-0.707	#74b2d4	0.45841	0.70031	0.83158	colour_06	
1909	8.95	-0.932	#3480b9	0.2066	0.50217	0.72673	colour_04	
1910	10.025	0.143	#edf2f5	0.92941	0.95005	0.9614	colour_10	
1911	10.68333	0.80133	#fac9b1	0.98101	0.79195	0.69494	colour_13	

9. Use the detailed document to plan your artwork. It contains two tables:
 - a. Table 1 - shows you which colours relate to individual years. Primarily, you will use the 'years' and 'colour' columns. The other columns are just for information. This will help you to know which colour relates to which year.
 - b. Table 2 - shows you the total number of each colour stripe. This will help you plan how much art materials you will need in each colour.

About the data and tool

At the time of writing, the tool only uses [temperature data from the Climatic Research Unit \(CRU\)](#), specifically:

University of East Anglia Climatic Research Unit; Harris, I.C.; Jones, P.D.; Osborn, T. (2024): CRU TS4.08: Climatic Research Unit (CRU) Time-Series (TS) version 4.08 of high-resolution gridded data of month-by-month variation in climate (Jan. 1901- Dec. 2023). NERC EDS Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, 10 March 2026. <https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/715abce1604a42f396f81db83aeb2a4b/>.

If the tool is updated, a new data citation will be provided and should be used instead of the one above.

The tool subsets the dataset to show only the required data for the custom climate stripe. It then assigns colour codes to the data for each coloured stripe in the visualisation. Colours represent deviations from the 1971-2000 average, with blues indicating cooler years and reds indicating warmer years. The data highlights significant warming trends, such as the

shift from predominantly blue/grey stripes in the early 20th century to deep reds in recent years.

Designing your artwork/craft project

Once you have your personalised colour-coded table, it can be applied to various creative mediums to create your artwork. The design process involves mapping specific years to colour codes (e.g., colour_01 to colour_20) and arranging them chronologically. Projects do not need to be rectangular; they could take the shape of animals or other symbols to highlight specific climate impacts. Below are some examples of personal projects.

Painting

Molly MacRae painted stripes showing temperature change in her local area (Oxford, UK)

Mosaic

Poppy Townsend used small mosaic tiles to show the changing climate in her hometown (Weymouth, UK) over her mum's lifespan (~60 years).

Crochet

Fiona Dickenson created a scarf using crochet based on data for Lyme Regis, UK.

Running a public engagement activity

In June 2024, we ran a week-long public engagement event at STFC Harwell Open Week.

Over 3 days, we made two 3.5m x 0.5m mosaics (or could be combined as one 3.5 x 1 metre mosaic) - representing our changing climate. Pictured below. The colours are based on real data for Harwell, Oxfordshire for the last ~140 years.

Here we reflect on some of the practicalities and logistics needed for organising the mosaic activity.

Essential materials include:

- glass mosaic tiles in varied colours corresponding to the data codes
- wood panels for the base
- non-toxic glue
- glue pots
- brushes
- spill kits (paper towels)
- first aid supplies
- wall fixtures (for displaying the artwork afterwards) - we used foldable table top easels so the artwork was portable
- grout (and grouting tools e.g. squeegee, buckets and sponge)

Optional materials:

- aprons
- hair ties
- tile cutters and protective goggles - these were used by staff only for creating words in the mosaic before the event started

In total, the resources cost approximately £1000 to create a single mosaic artwork measuring 3.5 metres x 1 metre (or two artworks measuring 3.5 metres by 0.5 metre if displayed separately).

We sourced the mosaic tiles and wooden panels from Hobby Island Mosaics (<https://hobby-island.co.uk/>).

We originally planned to create one artwork measuring 3.5m x 0.5m. However after two full days of school participation it was clear we would need more materials for the final public day.

In terms of people time - we spent approximately 2 days (with two members of staff) preparing the wood panels i.e. adding the data to the boards, adding cut tiles to spell out the word slogans. During the event we had between 2-4 people supporting each day of activity. Post-event we spent approximately 1 day grouting the final artwork.

You can read more about the team's [reflections and lessons learnt in this LinkedIn post](#).

Additional supporting materials (such as examples of risk assessment, spreadsheet for working out how many different colour tiles are needed, fact sheets, and briefing guides for volunteers) can be provided on request. Please contact support@ceda.ac.uk and reference this document alongside details of your request.